

"MU'IN UL-MURID" IS A POETIC HAGIOGRAPHIC WORK

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Annotation. The article focuses on the reasons for writing and genre features of the didactic work " Mu'in ul-murid " written in verse form, created in the 14th century in Eastern classical literature. A scientific attitude was expressed to the opinions about the author of the work. Also, the genre of wisdom in the works written in the hagiographic direction is defined and its characteristics are revealed.

Keywords and phrases. Poem didactic work, genre, hagiography, wisdom, quatrain, narration, composition.

We in the article XIV century Muslim hagiography about " Mu'in ul - murid" work to learn goal by doing that's all we got because of this period literature with getting to know if we go out Hagiographic works learned B. Nazarov Muslim hagiographic of literature formation and development three to the period be to learn not a slave that found " First period VIII - IX the century cover takes This period of hagiography main feature that 's it story being done events cover received to the period relatively is close also religious beliefs priority was. Second period from the 10th century starting from the 12th century the first half cover takes This period Muslim in hagiography First, different in the language works is created began , secondly , historicity from the feature according to artistic tissue and narration feature , ie to idealize attention increased. Third period XIII- XV centuries right will come During these periods Muslim the world Mongolian invaders oppression from the beginning he forgave and little by little this from

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oppression free is cultural life revived, as a result hagiographic again to literature need appear is past in centuries lived the sheikhs and of the saints life about story doer works increased ” [1.23], therefore for we object as precisely to the XIII-XIV centuries about hagiographic works of our choice that's why to the period belongs to hagiographic in the works artistry signs high and literary and artistic in terms of analysis to do himself justifies

this period Turk in the land islam religion in expansion continue did XIII-XIV centuries come hard worker of the people his opinion dry from preaching according to religious-mythical to events weight increase started The development of religious works in a certain sense in the literature of the Golden Horde was a natural phenomenon. Because for the country, which has just started to become an Islamic state, it was a necessary event to provide its inhabitants with works dedicated to pure faith. One of the important reasons for the emergence of prose works was the desire to artistically express various narratives based on a certain plot. The task of widely spreading religion among the people was performed by artistic and didactic works on religious topics.

Gold Horde literary in the environment surface came hagiographic from the works one is " Mu'in". ul-murid ". of the work the author who the fact that about two different to look available [2.186]. This to the matter thought stated without work the author We named Sheikh Sharif Khoja , the reason of the work heart and lust in the department as follows four cited :

Heart Nafs is soul result erur

Winner if one hangar face urur

Know this statement Sheikh Sharif Khoja's

Mabazi in a leech completeness type [3.53].

This four from the content work the author obviously is happening

The work the people honesty in the spirit education, Islamic beliefs to spread in order to to the world came Islam and of the Sufis main principles on the subject

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the work dates back to the 14th century Khorezm in the region to the world came of the work to science known has been the only one copy in Bursa writing and print old works stored in the library is stored. The work with different in years ZUTogan, F. Koprulu, J. Ekman, A. Bodrogleti, A. Karamanogli , N. Khalimov, Ch. Go'klenov , R. Toparli , M. Argunshah such as scientists learned, own thoughts stated. Book religious-mystical in content of the 407 fours written consists of, mutakarib in the sea (faulun foul foul foul). This is a work Recap Toparli in Turkey in 2008 and Mustafa Argunshah by again was studied and published [3.] . " Mu'in. " ul-murid " work poetic four in the form of written although separately to departments separated, har one the section is named. The work traditional praise and don't with begins with:

Thank you praise god district thousand to you

Muslim monotheist create manga

Elig handle you there is only one -u

In eclipse come on Yogurt is one to me

That is, " To God. " thousand thanks let me be God's to the unit believer Muslim by doing " You have created, " it began . Next sections : faith department

If you stay two on the agenda safe

The truth cheer up give up faith

If you ask who what happens to faith

Be aware I don't know let me do statement

that this chapter begins . That is , if two in the world (inner and apparently the world) is also alive stay if you say, sincerely in your heart faith bring Faith what that to know I will tell you if you want to give, next in quads skills to the presence, to the prophets and books, doomsday until from the heart to believe need and him language with confirmation need statement is given ; Allah and his prophet Muhammad to know about department in which "Kongilga Right do you know ?

"question with begins and to him the author answer gives Then second to the question passes:

"Messenger right If so, prove it is there ?"and answer gives:" evidence a lot if you if you don't mind I say"; sermon and advice department; different differet laws about department; tayammum about department ; zakat department; the will¹ department; manners department; about equality department; conversation department; sharia, tariqat and truth department; heart and lust department; leech (to sect enter) section; To God thanks to do and mention to do department such as named and that's us we know from naming It is possible that the work is literal hagiographic to the character belongs to Uzbek in literature this work yet enough not studied. This work study also Khorezm Turkish in learning object task passes . Which one in terms of work wisdom continue made let's say will be

One row in studies to wisdom as follows definition gives: "**Wisdom** - thinking qualification medium without to be app with done increasing, experience with attainable right knowledge; Right according to word everyone of the thing the most perfect wisdom God's army through it Allah of the saint to the heart power dedicates ; mystical to poems wisdom is called Hikmat - knowledge , wisdom , philosophy, secret , intelligence - and truth right coming thin meaningful short word, parable; of the item from the situation , apparently and inner mood debate doer science; ethics and to the truth circle useful brief word To God obedience; mind, word and in action harmony" [4.47]. That is, "Mu'in." ul-murid" work although of the fours organize found though , but content-essence in terms of to wisdom suitable falls Literary scholar scientist F. Kopruli: "From the 10th century starting from religious-mystical to works wisdom it is said" writes [5.119]. So that 's it kind of works comparative-analytical learning today's of our researchers in front of standing from tasks one to be we think it is necessary.

¹Irodat – 1. Qasd, niyat, xohish, istak. 2. Muridlik uchun pirga qo‘l bermoq, ya’ni o‘z irodasini ustozga topshirmoq. Sharti irodat – muridlik sharti.

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